

LSTM-BASED ESTIMATION OF ATTITUDE SENSOR RUL

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Abstract. This paper represents a framework for estimating the remaining useful life of satellite attitude sensor namely the angular rate gyro. First, data collection relies on the output of Kalman filter which estimates both attitude and gyro errors. Next, the LSTM model is fed with these data after processing for a more convenient learning. After training, the model is tested with new data aiming to explore its performance. The RMSE metric is used for assessing model performance where it showed good results with overall RMSE not exceeding 7%.

Keywords: Remaining useful life, angular rate gyro, Kalman filter, Long-Short term memory.

1 Introduction

Angular rate gyros are amongst the most important attitude sensors used in satellite precise pointing suitable for specific mission such as remote sensing and exoplanets discovery. However, these sensors are prone to failure which is supported statistically in many studies and reports [1-3]. Hence, for better preparation of the satellite lifetime ahead, mission operations team need to have an estimation of the gyro remaining useful life to prevent longer periods of post-failure adaptation. This paper explores the benefits of attitude estimation using the extended Kalman filter (EKF) to provide high quality data. These data are then used to train an LSTM deep learning model which is a typical choice for forecasting tasks such as stock market states, and RUL prediction [4-5].

2 Methodology

Our proposal incorporates Kalman filter estimates with LSTM-based RUL prediction. Taking into account the system state vector comprising angular rate, attitude quaternion, and gyro drifts, the extended Kalman filter (EKF) used in this paper is given by the following equations [6]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \omega_{k+1} \\ q_{k+1} \\ \beta_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_k \\ q_k \\ \beta_k \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -J^{-1}\omega_k \times (J\omega_k) + J^{-1}u_k \\ \frac{1}{2}\Omega_k\omega_k \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} dt + \begin{bmatrix} \Phi_{1k} \\ \frac{1}{2}\Omega_k\Phi_{2k} \\ \Phi_{3k} \end{bmatrix} dt \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \omega_{yk} \\ q_{yk} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} I_3 & 0_3 & I_3 \\ 0_3 & I_3 & 0_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \omega_k \\ q_k \\ \beta_k \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{1k} \\ \psi_{2k} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where the state vector $x_k = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_k \\ q_k \\ \beta_k \end{bmatrix}$, J is the satellite inertia tensor, u_k is the control torque, Ω_k is the kinematics matrix, and (Φ_i, ψ_i) are uncorrelated gaussian noises. After arranging the Jacobian and filter covariance matrices, the iteration is as follows:

$$\hat{x}_{k|k-1} = F(\hat{x}_{k-1|k-1}, u_{k-1}) \quad (3)$$

$$P_{k|k-1} = F_{k-1}P_{k-1|k-1}F_{k-1}^T + L_{k-1}Q_{k-1}L_{k-1}^T \quad (4)$$

$$\tilde{y}_k = y_k - H\hat{x}_{k|k-1} \quad (5)$$

$$S_k = HP_{k|k-1}H^T + R_k \quad (6)$$

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$$K_k = P_{k|k-1} H^T S_k^{-1} \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{x}_{k|k} = \hat{x}_{k|k-1} + K_k \tilde{y}_k \quad (8)$$

$$P_{k|k} = (I - K_k H) P_{k|k-1} \quad (9)$$

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41 The above equations describe the EKF steps namely: prediction, innovation, and update. Choosing EKF
42 in our approach relies on the efficiency of such filter especially in slow dynamics such as satellite attitude
43 control. EKF incorporates measurements from star sensor and gyro in the so-called sensor fusion scheme
44 to provide accurate angular rate estimates [7].

45 Even though the quaternion values are inherently normalized ($-1 < q < 1$) [7], the angular rate and gyro
46 drifts are far from being normalized. Hence, a preprocessing normalization step is performed before using
47 these data in LSTM training [8]. The RUL prediction framework proposed in this paper is illustrated in
48 Figure 1 and LSTM hyperparameters are listed in Table 1.

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Figure 1. RUL prediction framework proposed in this paper.

Table 1. LSTM structure adopted in this work.

Parameter	Value
Input shape	10
# of LSTM	200
Return sequence	True
Dropout	0.2
# of Dense in the hidden layer	100
Dropout	0.25
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.002

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57 3 Results

58 3.1. Data setting

59 In data preparation, the measurements of 200 simulated gyros were used to provide the LSTM training
60 with rich data covering multiple aspects of drift time and slope which reflects different real-life scenarios
61 while preserving plausible data range inspired from the datasheets of internationally known
62 manufacturers in the space industry [9]. Combined with star sensor quaternion, the aforementioned
63 angular rates are then fed to the EKF to estimate the satellite attitude and gyro errors.

64 **3.2. RUL prediction**

65 The learning curve is shown in Figure 2. After saving the LSTM-based RUL prediction model, it was
 66 used to predict the RUL of primarily reserved gyro for the test purpose. Figures 3 illustrates these results
 67 for 3 randomly selected samples. Also, the percentage RMSE of two random batches are displayed in
 68 Table 2.

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Figure 2. LSTM learning curve.

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Figure 3. RUL prediction results for 3 random samples.

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Table 2. Percentage RMSE obtained for two random batches.

Batch #	RMSE (cycles)	Percentage RMSE (%)
1	659	6.6
2	475	4.7

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76 4 Discussion

77 The results show that our proposal is able to predict the RUL of satellite gyros with good accuracy which
 78 is reflected by a percentage RMSE reaching less than 7%, however, during the sensor's beginning of life
 79 the RUL value might be not always accurate due to test conditions. The reason behind this is that the
 80 model is trained on data that can be similar to the test data in sensor healthy state which led to
 81 discrepancy between training and testing in this phase (overfitting) [8]. However, this discrepancy is
 82 reduced after the beginning of degradation because the pre-failure signature is much clearer in the
 83 features at that phase.

84 5 Conclusion

85 In this paper, an EKF-enhanced LSTM model was proposed to predict the remaining useful life of attitude
 86 sensors namely the angular rate gyros. After filtering the attitude state (angular rate, attitude quaternion,
 87 and gyro errors) using the extended Kalman filter, and after adequate pre-processing, the LSTM model is
 88 fed with these data to learn how to predict the RUL accurately, which was shown in the result section.
 89 Future work will focus on augmenting the feature space with further processed data to enhance RUL
 90 prediction performance.

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